

ACROSS BORDERS AND CLASSROOMS: EXPLORING CURRICULUM THROUGH STUDENT MOBILITY

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 12 August 2025 Revised: 14 Sept 2025 Accepted: 21 Oct 2025 Published: 1 Nov 2025</p>	<p>This study explores outbound student mobility as a form of curriculum inquiry rather than a mere administrative mechanism of internationalisation. Drawing on a qualitative case study of nine undergraduates from a northern university in Malaysia, placed at three Indonesian universities, data were gathered through semi-structured interviews and reflective journals to capture students' lived experiences. Thematic analysis revealed three interrelated dimensions of learning: academic and intercultural development, challenges and coping strategies, and perceptions of institutional support. Students described mobility as a transformative curriculum beyond classrooms, where informal peer interactions and community engagement became powerful sites of learning. However, they also encountered structural frictions, including unclear credit transfer processes, administrative fragmentation, and inadequate pre-departure preparation. Coping strategies centred on peer support, self-regulation, and reframing adversity as growth. These findings highlight the hidden curriculum of mobility, encompassing emotional, financial, and bureaucratic negotiations that shape students' resilience and agency. The study concludes that mobility should be reframed as praxis which is an integrated curriculum experience where administrative systems, peer ecologies, and lived challenges collectively construct learning. It recommends that institutions embed holistic preparation, structured peer mentoring, and multidimensional assessment frameworks to enhance the educational value of mobility programs in Malaysia and the wider region.</p>
<p>Keywords: Student mobility, Curriculum as praxis, Hidden curriculum, Intercultural learning, Transformative education</p> <p> OPEN ACCESS</p>	

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INTRODUCTION

Student mobility has gained global prominence as a catalyst for academic enrichment, intercultural engagement, and employability in an increasingly connected world. Contemporary analyses reaffirm this momentum. The OECD Education at a Glance 2024 report notes that international student flows continue to rise, providing learners with competencies and cultural exposure rarely accessible in domestic settings, particularly within professional and STEM disciplines (OECD, 2024). Parallel regional studies reveal that many Southeast Asian students are now opting for intra-regional destinations, motivated by affordability, shared cultural proximity, and strengthened educational ties (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2024).

Malaysia stands at an interesting crossroads in this landscape to function both as a sender and as an emerging destination in international higher education. National policies promoting outbound exchanges and ASEAN collaborations reflect a strategic effort to enhance graduate competitiveness and global employability (Phillips, 2022). Simultaneously, Malaysia's growing attraction for inbound students through branch campuses and transnational programs reinforces its image as an education hub (Sivaperumal, 2024). Within this dual positioning, mobility should be reconceptualised not simply as an administrative or credit-transfer process but as a form of curriculum inquiry, where students encounter institutional realities, negotiate diverse contexts, and achieve transformative learning experiences.

While mobility has long been celebrated as a pillar of higher education internationalisation that is intended to develop global awareness, adaptability, and intercultural competence, emerging evidence exposes enduring gaps between policy ambitions and on-the-ground realities. Pellegrino et al. (2024) highlight that poor planning and limited preparation can hinder academic success among mobile students, while Yee and Hassan (2024) observe that Malaysian universities continue to face challenges such as inconsistent credit recognition, inadequate advisory support, and uneven institutional readiness. These findings reveal that without robust structural alignment, the educational potential of mobility may remain unrealised.

Equally significant are the emotional and adaptive dimensions of student mobility, which institutions often overlook. Research shows that students confront psychological strain, identity shifts, and cross-cultural adjustment alongside their academic commitments (Gomes & Wells, 2023). In Malaysia, international students have reported considerable stress and mental health concerns, often depending on peers and informal networks for emotional support (Mohamad & Ali, 2025). Such evidence nuances the dominant success narrative of mobility by bringing attention to its hidden emotional and social demands.

Despite these complexities, the transformative promise of mobility persists. Students frequently describe gaining independence, intercultural awareness, and deeper academic motivation where these outcomes were consistently observed across global mobility studies (Pellegrino et al., 2024). Yet in Malaysia, institutional emphasis remains largely quantitative, focusing on credit recognition and program throughput, with limited engagement in understanding broader developmental outcomes. This qualitative case study of outbound mobility at Universiti Utara Malaysia (UUM) therefore explores three key dimensions: the sufficiency of institutional preparation and support, the challenges and coping strategies experienced by students, and the transformative learning that results. Framing

mobility as a lived curriculum underscores its potential to shape not only academic trajectories but also students' resilience, self-concept, and global outlook.

Review of relevant literature

Outbound student mobility offers a fertile context for curriculum inquiry because it reveals how learning extends beyond the boundaries of formal syllabi. This study draws on two complementary perspectives, curriculum as praxis and the hidden curriculum, to explore how institutional design intersects with lived student experience.

Grundy (1987) reconceptualises curriculum not as a static body of content or a sequential process of instruction, but as praxis which is an informed, moral, and political act in which reflection and action are inseparable. This builds upon Freire's (1970) conception of praxis as the dialectical relationship between critical reflection and transformative action. Within the context of mobility, this view underscores how students must navigate tensions between institutional structures and real-world challenges. Administrative difficulties in credit transfer, technological barriers such as IMEI registration, and unexpected financial pressures become sites where students demonstrate agency and problem-solving skills. Recent scholarship has shown that international learning does not merely add new knowledge but reshapes students' identities through processes of adaptation and critical reflection (Leask and Bridge, 2023; Tran and Vu, 2018). When understood as praxis, mobility becomes curriculum in action, where students' knowledge is deepened through practical encounters that demand resilience, adaptability, and moral awareness.

At the same time, the hidden curriculum provides a complementary lens for understanding the unplanned dimensions of mobility. Students frequently acquire competencies that are rarely included in formal learning outcomes, such as financial literacy through budgeting, bureaucratic navigation in managing visas or credit transfer, intercultural communication in adapting to new linguistic and social contexts, and emotional regulation in dealing with isolation or uncertainty. Jackson's (1968) foundational work demonstrated that schools convey values, norms, and dispositions beyond the intended curriculum. Later scholars extended this analysis to higher education, showing how institutional cultures, power structures, and implicit expectations shape learning (Giroux, 2001; Margolis, 2001). Contemporary research (Beelen and Jones, 2015; Killick, 2021) argues that these hidden forms of learning are often more enduring than formally assessed achievements, yet they remain underrepresented in policy discourses that privilege measurable outcomes such as throughput and employability. By foregrounding the hidden curriculum, this study draws attention to the subtle but transformative learning that mobility makes possible.

Although policy frameworks continue to promote mobility as a means of developing global competence and employability, empirical studies reveal persistent misalignments between policy intention and lived experience (Kapfudzaruwa, 2024; Lomer, 2023). Viewing mobility as a curricular rather than administrative phenomenon makes it possible to understand how institutional systems, informal learning, and student agency interact to produce complex educational outcomes. One of the most pressing challenges concerns the inconsistency of credit transfer and workload recognition. Impola and Hölttä (2025) observe that frameworks such as the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System often fail to reflect the actual labour students invest, leading to inequities that disadvantage participants. These challenges are compounded in cross border contexts, where fragmented regional frameworks and varying institutional readiness make credit recognition unpredictable (Chao, 2020; Umemiya et al., 2024). Hill and Craig (2024) further show that uncertainty surrounding transferability influences students' decisions to participate in mobility programs, revealing how institutional design directly shapes participation. From a curriculum-as-

praxis perspective, these inconsistencies compel students to engage in negotiation, reflection, and improvisation, transforming mobility into a process of active inquiry rather than a simple academic exchange.

In addition to structural challenges, recent research has drawn attention to the emotional and adaptive dimensions of mobility. Students frequently encounter cultural dissonance, bureaucratic uncertainty, and financial strain with limited institutional support (Nguyen and Pham, 2024; Pawar and Devkar, 2024). Soheili (2025) highlights that peer networks and social resilience play a central role in helping students cope with stress, pointing to tacit learning processes that occur outside the formal curriculum. The rise of virtual mobility during and after the pandemic provides further evidence of this shift. Cheng (2023) as well as Zayim Kurtay and Ersay (2025) note that while online mobility expanded access, it also transferred logistical and emotional burdens to students, who were required to manage time zones, technical limitations, and reduced cultural immersion largely on their own. This dynamic complicates the celebratory discourse surrounding mobility by exposing the unrecognised labour and emotional investment that students contribute.

Despite these difficulties, a growing body of research confirms that mobility can lead to deep and lasting transformation when it is well supported. Numerous studies have documented gains in intercultural understanding, self-efficacy, and professional readiness (Goldstein, 2022; Huang and Cakmak, 2023). However, these benefits are not automatic. Davis et al. (2021) and Bartel Radic et al. (2025) demonstrate that factors such as program duration, host context, and the quality of intercultural interaction determine the depth of learning achieved. Li et al. (2025) further show that in the ASEAN region, meaningful engagement with host communities contributes more strongly to student development than participation alone. These insights reinforce the view that mobility represents a curricular space where intended, hidden, and emergent learning interact in complex and productive ways.

Analysing mobility through the dual perspectives of curriculum as praxis and the hidden curriculum helps reconcile these tensions. It illuminates how structural design, adaptive struggle, and unacknowledged learning shape the overall experience. This perspective repositions mobility not as a peripheral policy mechanism but as a form of curriculum inquiry that captures the moral, intellectual, and relational dimensions of education in a globalised world.

Research Objectives and Methodological Approach

This study aimed at understanding how participation in a mobility program shapes students' academic, personal, and intercultural development; discovering the challenges faced by students in mobility programs and the coping strategies they develop and; exploring how institutional preparation and support influence students' mobility experiences.

This study adopted a qualitative case study approach to explore the lived experiences of outbound student mobility in depth. The case study design was selected because it allows for a detailed investigation of a bounded system situated within its authentic educational context, capturing the complexity of human experience that cannot be separated from its environment (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016; Yin, 2018). In contrast to experimental or survey designs, a case study privileges depth over generalisation, offering a holistic understanding of how institutional structures, student agency, and curriculum processes interact. As Stake (1995) notes, the strength of this approach lies in its capacity

to centre participants' voices and subjective meanings which is an essential consideration when examining student mobility as both an institutional and personal journey.

The participants comprised nine undergraduate students from Universiti Utara Malaysia representing programmes in Information Technology, Accounting, Counselling, and Moral Education. Purposive sampling was used following Patton's (2015) principle of selecting information-rich cases that yield the most insight. The participants were identified based on three main criteria: excellent academic performance demonstrated by the Dean's Award, active engagement in co-curricular activities, and successful completion of institutional screening interviews for mobility eligibility. They were placed for one semester of fourteen weeks in three Indonesian universities. This form of criterion-based purposive sampling allowed for the inclusion of students who were both academically capable and institutionally endorsed, strengthening the credibility and interpretive depth of the data.

Data were drawn from two principal sources: semi structured interviews and written reflections. The interviews provided space for open dialogue and probing of emerging issues while maintaining focus across participants (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2015). Questions explored motivations, institutional and personal challenges, coping mechanisms, and perceived outcomes of the experience. In addition, students' written reflections before departure and upon return offered first-hand accounts of their evolving perspectives, thereby complementing interview data. The integration of these two sources allowed for triangulation, which Denzin and Lincoln (2018) describe as essential to achieving trustworthiness by capturing both real-time experiences and retrospective insights.

The data were analysed thematically following the six iterative phases outlined by Braun and Clarke (2017): familiarisation, generation of codes, identification of themes, review of patterns, definition of themes, and final reporting. The initial phase involved open coding to inductively generate early categories, followed by axial coding to identify relationships among structural, emotional, and transformative dimensions (Charmaz, 2014). Selective coding was then used to consolidate key themes aligned with the theoretical perspectives of curriculum as praxis and the hidden curriculum. Ethical considerations guided every stage of the research process. Participants were fully briefed about the study's aims and their right to withdraw before providing informed consent. To enhance instrument reliability, pilot interviews were conducted with students of similar profiles, and feedback was obtained from two associate professors specialising in curriculum studies. The research adhered to Lincoln and Guba's (1985) framework for trustworthiness. Credibility was established through triangulation, member validation, and peer debriefing; dependability was ensured through systematic documentation of all procedures; confirmability was supported by reflexive journaling and an audit trail; and transferability was promoted through detailed contextual descriptions (Shenton, 2004). Collectively, these measures strengthened the methodological integrity and analytic transparency of the study, ensuring that the findings authentically represented participants' experiences and meanings.

Findings of the study

The findings are presented in alignment with the three guiding research questions to provide a coherent narrative of students' experiences in the outbound mobility program. Drawing from both

interview transcripts and reflective journals, the analysis reveals a dynamic interplay between motivation, challenges, coping mechanisms, and the perceived adequacy of institutional support.

RQ1: In what ways do students perceive their academic, personal, and intercultural growth as outcomes of participating in a mobility program?

Participants consistently viewed the mobility experience not as a short academic visit but as a transformative stage of holistic education. The academic component was described through exposure to new pedagogical styles that differed from their home university practices. Students frequently contrasted the participatory and discussion-based learning abroad with the more lecture-centred approaches they were used to. For instance, Student F reflected, “Most classes involved discussion, not just the lecturer talking... it gave me space to think critically and speak confidently.” Similarly, Student A stated during an interview, “Students can benefit from a more relaxed and interactive learning environment.”

Personal growth emerged as another dominant theme, particularly around independence, adaptability, and emotional maturity. Several students shared that living abroad required them to manage responsibilities they had previously relied on family for. Student B expressed, “Being far from my family was a big challenge because I always relied on them... but in Indonesia I realised I can live independently and adapt easily.” Student C also affirmed this development, noting, “This experience helped me to become more confident, more mature, and more open-minded.” Such accounts reveal how mobility encouraged the cultivation of autonomy and reflective awareness, traits the students later linked to their professional identities as future educators.

Intercultural learning was intertwined with daily life, extending beyond classroom encounters. Students described cultural understanding as emerging through social interactions, communal meals, and leisure activities. Student D observed, “The mobility program was an opportunity to learn about another country’s culture and way of life... I could experience the atmosphere of another country myself.” For Student E, intercultural engagement contributed to professional and moral values: “Through intercultural sharing, we collectively developed values such as embracing diversity.” Collectively, the data portray mobility as a curriculum beyond the formal curriculum, where academic enrichment, personal growth, and cultural learning were interwoven dimensions of transformation.

RQ2: What challenges do students encounter during mobility, and how do they cope with them?

Students’ accounts reveal that their challenges were multifaceted, extending beyond economic hardship. Financial issues were compounded by administrative inefficiencies, unclear procedures, and institutional rigidity. Student A noted, “At first, I faced financial constraints and issues with adding subjects for credit transfer.” Similarly, Student B mentioned the impact of digital bureaucracy: “The IMEI registration issue meant we could not access mobile data... I had to buy a second-hand phone just to get internet.” Another challenge was poor coordination at host universities. One reflection described, “The faculty administration was disorganised and inconsistent... it made things difficult when we had to deal with two faculties like FKIP and Psychology.”

Health concerns were also cited, reminding students of the unpredictability of studying abroad. Student D shared, “One of us had to be admitted to hospital due to health problems... we learned about the private healthcare system in Indonesia.” Despite these challenges, students demonstrated remarkable adaptability.

Coping strategies drew upon both individual and collective resources. Peer support was particularly significant, functioning as a space for emotional stability and joint problem-solving. Student B

explained, “We always exchanged opinions and shared our problems,” while Student D added, “I depended on my friends... we made decisions together with maturity.” Students also found personal outlets for stress through creative or leisure activities. Student G wrote, “I tried new foods on the streets of Jakarta and also returned to hobbies like painting and photography.” Student H reframed adversity positively: “I tried to see things from a positive angle, considering it a process of learning.” Thus, coping was not limited to endurance but involved reflective adaptation and meaning-making that deepened their resilience.

RQ3: How do students perceive the adequacy of institutional guidance and support in preparing for and navigating the mobility program?

Students generally perceived a gap between institutional expectations and actual support. The most common concern was insufficient clarity about credit transfer processes. Student C stated, “UUM needs to update the information about credit transfer on its website so students are not confused.” Similarly, Student E explained, “It should be explained clearly who to consult at the host university for course outlines before filling in the forms.” Such administrative ambiguities created unnecessary stress and delays in class registration.

Students also pointed out the lack of practical preparation for logistical and cultural adaptation. Student E remarked, “UUM should give clear explanations in advance about IMEI, transportation, and insurance.” Without proper guidance, students learned through trial and error, which they found both challenging and instructive. Several recommended more comprehensive pre-departure sessions that addressed not only academic issues but also local customs, financial management, and technological systems. As Student A proposed, “If possible, UUM should conduct a thorough briefing about culture and cost of living.”

While institutional shortcomings were acknowledged, students simultaneously valued how these gaps fostered independence and problem-solving skills. However, the recurring theme of misalignment between institutional policy and lived experience underscores the need for a more integrated approach to supporting mobility programs that treats student development as both academic and human growth.

Discussion, recommendations and conclusion

This case study reveals a nuanced landscape of outbound student mobility that both corroborates and complicates dominant claims in recent scholarship. Students consistently portrayed mobility as a catalyst for academic, personal, and intercultural development, yet they emphasised that the most profound learning occurred in informal, relational, and peer-based settings. This supports the argument that experiential encounters and everyday practices during study abroad are often the decisive triggers for intercultural growth rather than mobility itself (Mu and Wei, 2022). Students’ reflections on dialogic classrooms, flexible pacing, and community-oriented activities echo recent findings that intentional pedagogical design and structured intercultural engagement significantly enhance learning outcomes (Jin, 2024). Likewise, their experiences resonate with research showing that internationalisation-at-home partnerships can foster authentic cross-cultural dialogue and perspective transformation (Dong et al., 2024).

Notably, students located their development within small peer ecologies, where belonging and co-regulation emerged as the key mechanisms of learning. This insight extends existing frameworks by illustrating communicative resilience as an emergent property of student interaction and mutual care. The finding aligns with growing evidence that communication-based resilience strengthens

adaptation among international students (Fanari and Segrin, 2025) and that peer-led programs improve socioemotional outcomes (Parmar et al., 2025).

At a structural level, the findings expose persistent procedural frictions that continue to limit the educational promise of mobility in the region. Uncertainty surrounding course approval, fragmented coordination between faculties, and slow credit transfer reflect broader regional challenges documented across Asia and Southeast Asia (Umemiya, 2024; ASEAN, 2025). These issues are not peripheral inconveniences but active curriculum forces that shape student experience and learning. Administrative opacity and late scheduling effectively reallocate time and cognitive energy from academic engagement to bureaucratic survival. This observation supports recent scholarship linking institutional governance and policy coherence to the realised educational value of mobility initiatives (Aguiar et al., 2024). The findings thus affirm the need to conceptualise mobility management as a curriculum process in its own right, rather than as a purely logistical concern.

A further insight concerns the hidden curriculum of mobility, which comprises the less visible demands of financial triage, bureaucratic navigation, and technological adaptation, such as IMEI registration. Scholars have increasingly revisited the idea of hidden curriculum in international education, particularly in contexts marked by uneven access and evolving equality frameworks (Baykut, 2022; Brooks and Waters, 2022). The present data demonstrate that these hidden demands are not incidental but formational: through them, students develop agency, judgment, and confidence. While mobility is often celebrated as a pathway to cultural capital, this study reveals that much of the growth stems from navigating unstructured stressors and finding social buffers in peer communities. This aligns with recent studies on unmet mental health needs among international cohorts and the role of collective care in sustaining wellbeing (Sakız, 2024; Ji et al., 2024). It also reinforces calls to centre student agency as a primary analytical lens in mobility research (Inouye and McAlister, 2022). An interesting divergence emerges in the relative significance assigned to formal coursework. Students described classroom learning as less central than the broader ecology of relationships, routines, and problem-solving encounters that structured their daily lives. This view challenges output-driven models that measure mobility success through credits and grades alone. While recent debates have begun to critique such narrow evaluation frameworks, they often continue to privilege formal academic outcomes (Van Mol et al., 2022). The present study argues for a broader curriculum frame that places praxis and hidden learning processes at the core of internationalisation.

Three key contributions arise from this inquiry. First, it specifies how peer micro-ecologies nurture intercultural and personal development through communicative resilience. Second, it demonstrates that administrative clarity, credit recognition, and governance structures are not peripheral management issues but curriculum conditions that directly influence learning. Third, it positions mobility as praxis, showing that the hidden curriculum of adaptation, negotiation, and problem solving constitutes meaningful educational terrain.

These insights invite Malaysian universities and regional partners to reconceptualise mobility as curriculum-in-action rather than as an administrative extension. Institutional preparation should move beyond credit listings and orientation briefings by embedding pre-departure praxis workshops that simulate likely bureaucratic and technological challenges such as IMEI registration or course approval delays. Structured peer ecologies could be intentionally developed through alumni mentoring schemes and facilitated intercultural reflection circles, converting coping experiences into deliberate learning. Mobility assessment should also adopt a multidimensional framework that recognises hidden curriculum achievements such as resilience, agency, and financial literacy, alongside formal academic indicators. Reflective digital portfolios could be used to capture this holistic development and inform future program design.

Ultimately, this study underscores that outbound mobility is neither a seamless continuation of classroom learning nor a form of cultural tourism. It is a lived curriculum in which institutional systems, peer relations, and unanticipated challenges interact to shape academic, personal, and intercultural trajectories. While participants demonstrated remarkable adaptability and transformative growth, their narratives expose enduring structural and administrative gaps that demand curricular attention. By embracing mobility as praxis and acknowledging the hidden curriculum at work, higher education institutions in Malaysia and beyond can move toward more holistic and equitable internationalisation. In doing so, mobility programs can transcend the logic of credit accumulation to become genuine sites of transformative education, preparing students for uncertain and interconnected futures.

Co-Author Contribution

All Author carried out the fieldwork, prepared the literature review and overlooked the whole article's write up.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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